

Environment scenario : A mega scan from the big bang to the third millenium[†]

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Abstract : According to recent estimate, the age of the Universe is 13.7 billion years following the Big Bang event. The elements were created in the early stage of the Universe and embedded in the solar systems and hence into the planets including our Earth. In the time scale of evolution Man came last of all some 0.0025–0.0030 billion years age under optimum environment of pure air, pure water and pure land as well as forest cover. The history of the progress of human civilisation in terms of science and technology is virtually the history of environmental degradation. Some crucial environmental issues threatening human survival are briefly discussed – Global Warming, Biodiversity, Water Crisis, Human Development. India's Environmental Heritage is also highlighted.

Keywords : Environment, pollution, global warming, biodiversity, greenhouse effect.

Prelude

It is a rare honour and privilege to have a Symposium of the Chemists' Convention in my name. I am grateful to the Indian Chemical Society and the Council of the Society for their kind gesture and goodwill. The nice compliments from the Symposium Chairman, Prof. D. Banerjee (ex-President of the Indian Chemical Society) and Prof. D. C. Mukherjee (Secretary, Indian Chemical Society) are bit heavy for an individual and so quite logically, I would like to share these with my research associates who helped me in conducting my research projects successfully for over three decades.

I consider my address incomplete without presenting a token gift in the form of a mini-lecture to my distinguished audience.

The Big Bang

The entire matter of the Universe was condensed into a tiny sphere of dust and gas, which after consecutive contractions and expansions, finally exploded with tremendous violence, hurling into space thousands of fragments of core matter while releasing million degrees centigrade temperature and considerable energy. This was the phenomenon of the Big Bang occurring 13.7 billion years ago.

The cosmic objects vanished long long ago but the primordial light or "after glow" of the Big Bang fireball is still travelling across the Universe. Very recently

Alexander Kashlinsky, Head of a team of astronomers of NASA Goddard Space Flight Centre at Greenland reported in *Nature* (2005) (cited by Steve Connor in *Independent*, London, November 2005) on the probable sequence of the Big Bang events. Kashlinsky captured the "afterglow" by Infra-red camera, fitted on Spitzer Space telescope.

Fig. 1. The Big Bang

The Big Bang marked the dawn of Time, followed by the formation of massive First Stars, Supernova embedded with elements just created, Star forming clouds and the Modern Universe containing some 100000 galaxies. All these events took place in 13.7 billion years.

Creation of elements : It is intriguing that elements were created and the process completed within 30 min in the early stage of the Universe and embedded in the stars and galaxies and therefrom into the solar systems and planets. In the fiery environment of stars where temperature ranged upto 100 million degrees centigrade the nuclear

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Effet or Global Warming.

The sources of CO₂ are fossil fuel combustion, auto exhausts and factory emissions while the sinks are the oceans and green plants (photosynthesis). These sinks absorb about 50% of total CO₂ emission. The net increase is 11 billion tons of CO₂ per year. This can be cut down to 50% if we can stop deforestation.

It may be noted that CO₂ serves as global thermostat, resetting the Earth's temperature as CO₂ level rises and falls. It regulates global temperature to life-sustaining 15 °C for 3 billion years. Without CO₂ the Earth would be as cold as the Moon and lifeless while with too much CO₂, it would also be lifeless as the neighbouring planet, Venus with surface temperature of over 450 °C.

Besides CO₂ (Greenhouse effect 50%), other greenhouse gases are CH₄ (19%), CFC (17%), O₃ (8%), N₂O (4%) and H₂O (2%).

A slight increase in surface temperature, say 1 °C, as a result of global warming can adversely affect the global climate, food production and threaten the survival of islands and coastal cities.

Recently in March, 2002 a huge chunk of Larsen B ice shelf in Antarctica sheered away into the sea – it was roughly of the size of Luxembourg (Europe). In 1995 Larsen A (smaller neighbour) broke off and much bigger ice shelves may follow. According to U.S. and British scientists, engaged in Antarctic Survey, the ice shelf on Antarctic peninsula had entered a phase of rapid break-up with more than 50 billion tons of ice spilling into the Weddel sea to form thousands of massive icebergs. Scientists have measured a 2.5 °C rise in temperature in the Antarctic peninsula over the past 50 years and they believe that this can be linked to global warming and climate change exacerbated by man-made pollution.

Greenhouse effect is partly counter balanced by loading of particulate matter into the atmosphere from natural

Fig. 3. Iceshelf collapse in Antarctica

and man-made sources but it has definitely led to rise in temperature – 0.5–0.6 °C in the last 100 years at a slower pace than anticipated. However, it has been challenged at some political levels and their views are shared by a few scientists. But on the whole, it lacks scientific bias, as revealed by the UN Inter-Governmental Panel on Climate change (2001) and UN Earth Summit (Rio, 1992) on curtailment of greenhouse gas emissions.

Biodiversity

Forests are important bioreserves. Most of the 1700 million hectares of tropical forests are located in the developing countries. While they cover barely 7% of the land surface, they nurture 50% of the world's flora and fauna. India is very rich in biological diversity. It is estimated that about 45000 species of plants occur in India. The position of the Indian sub-continent at the confluence of three biogeographic realms is an important contributing factor and explains the presence of African, Mediterranean, European, Sino-Japanese and Indo-Malayan elements in the flora and fauna in India. This has made India a "gene bank" for several food crops, forest trees, medicinal and aromatic plants and domesticated animals.

But for satisfaction of our needs and greed in constant pursuit of better living standards, we are destroying forests recklessly. Natural extinction, part of evolutionary process, has been accelerated by man-made extinction wave. The net result is that about 10% of the species have been eliminated during the past 100 years. India is losing 1.3 million hectares of forest each year while losing one plant and one animal species each day. This extinction of species or **specide** is more serious a crime than **genocide**. It is in our interest of survival that we should conserve our plant, animal and micro-organism (bacteria and fungi) wealth.

There is growing realisation all over the world about the urgent need to conserve the biodiversity. The Rio Summit of the United Nations (1992) adopted the Treaty on Biodiversity whereby the countries agreed to conserve the biodiversity – the living natural resources (plants, animals, microbes etc.) for the welfare of mankind. The Johannesburg Summit (2002) endorsed the Treaty.

Water Crisis

The threat of water famine looms large as the life lines of the countries i.e. the river systems are being poisoned year after year with the waste of urbanisation and industrialisation. A typical case study of water pollution is that of the Ganga pollution in India (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Ganga pollution.

Monitoring of the water quality in terms of the standard parameters reveals that the upper stretch (Rishikesh upstream of Kanpur) is the best clean range (D.O. 5-9; BOD less than 2) while Kanpur, 50 km downstream (45 tanneries, 10 textile mills, 2 jute mills and many chemical and pharmaceutical units) is polluted (D.O. 5-9; BOD 10-50); Varanasi is the second polluted zone (D.O. 5-9; BOD 4-24) while the Hooghly river near Kolkata is the most polluted zone (150 industries – 87 jute mills, 12 textile mills, 7 tanneries, 5 paper mills, 4 distilleries along with domestic sewage from 360 outfalls on both sides of the river). The Ganga Action Plan (1986) was formulated by the Central Government to clean up the Ganga river by tackling the problems of sewage pollution and industrial pollution but its implementation is far from encouraging.

With increasing water pollution, fresh water is getting more and more scarce. At present about 1 billion people around the world in 31 countries (mostly in the middle East and Africa) face water shortages. By 2025 this number will rise to 2.8 billion people and 17 more countries will join the list – Inida, Ethiopia, Kenya, Nigeria and Peru.

The UN Report (John Hopkin Institute Study) calls for a "Blue Revolution" to conserve and manage fresh water just as the Green Revolution in the 1960s sought to transform agricultural scenario. There are symptoms of the Blue Revolution in India – rainwater harvesting, drip irrigation, water recycling etc.

P-Triangle and Human Development

Population is intimately related to environment. The global population has grown faster in the 20th century than ever before – it doubled in 40 years between 1950 and 1990 to cross 5 billion. India's population has grown from 238 million to 1.02 billion between 1901 and 2001, ranking second to China (1.265 billion). By 2025 India is most likely to overtake China and become the most popu-

lous country in the world. India is trapped in the vicious P-Triangle – Population-Poverty-Pollution like other developing countries. This vicious P-Triangle must be broken for our survival.

The development status of a country is judged since 1993 by UNDP (United Nations Development Programme) in terms of the Human Development Index (HDI) in preference to GDP, previously used. HDI is based on three parameters – life span, literacy and living standard which determine the quality of life in a country. The latest (2000) HDI rankings of the various countries are shown below :

- (1) Canada, (2) Norway, (3) USA, (4) Australia, (5) Sweden, (6) Belgium, (7) Netherland, (8) Finland,.....
- (80) Sri Lanka,..... (128) India,..... (135) Pakistan,.....
- (146) Bangladesh.

The low ranking of India (128) is quite obvious. Its GDP (per capita) is \$ 300 – 1.28% of Japan (\$ 24000) and 2.5% of USA (\$ 20000). In spite of remarkable advances in science and technology, India still remains one of the very poor countries with 40% population below poverty line without access to safe drinking water as well as sanitary latrines and with the largest illiterate population (400 million).

India's Environmental Heritage

India has a rich environmental heritage dating back to the Vedic era some 5000 years ago. Isho-Upanishad of the Vedic period gave us this message :

"Isha Vashyamidam Sarbam

Yatkincha Jagatyam Jagat

Tena Tyaktena Bhunjeethah

Ma Gridhah Kasyachit Dhanam"

This means that the Universe is created by God. Give up your greed and enjoy the bounties of Nature. This is the key concept of Nature's conservation laid down 5000 years ago but we lost it and surprisingly enough, we are seized at present with this issue in the light of Western concepts.

The Nobel-laureate world poet and Founder of Visva-Bharati, Rabindra Nath Tagore introduced the practice of **Vriksha-ropan** (Tree Plantation) in 1928 at Santiniketan when nobody in the world was aware of its impact on environment.

Mahatma Gandhi, Father of the Nation, used to announce in his public meetings, echoing the message of Upanishada : "Nature has enough to satisfy everyone's need but not everyone's greed."

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Inspite of our rich environmental heritage, we lag behind the Western countries in the areas of environmental awareness. Why and how did it happen? This can be the topic of a National Symposium in future.

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